

NOTES

6-Hydroxymethyl angolensate from *Swietenia mahagoni* Jacq¹.

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In the previous communications we reported three terpenoid constituents, mahoganin², 7-deacetyl-7-oxo gedunin³ and cyclomahogenol⁴ from *S. mahagoni* Jacq. We now report the isolation of a new furanolactone, which was eventually identified as 6-hydroxy methyl angolensate (I) isolated from *Khaya grandifoliola* by Connolly *et al.*⁵.

The compound m.p. 235–38°, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ 90° (CHCl₃) was found to be homogeneous by the thin layer chromatography using the solvent system, benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) containing 2% methanol (R_f value 0.45). From analytical data the molecular formula C₂₇H₃₄O₈ was assigned to this compound. This has also been confirmed by mass spectral measurements when a molecular ion peak at m/e 486 was observed. The ir. spectrum of the compound shows bands at 3475 (hydroxyl), 1724 (δ -lactone, carbomethoxy, cyclohexanone) and 1505 and 875 cm⁻¹ (furan ring). The uv. absorption maxima characteristic for furan at 211 m μ (log ϵ 3.69) and for ketonic function at 275 m μ (log ϵ 1.42) was recorded.

The N.M.R. spectrum of the compound (60 MHz in CDCl₃) showed the presence of two α -furan protons (δ 7.3–7.5); β -furan proton (δ 6.4); one furfurylic proton (δ 5.65); protons for a carbomethoxy group (δ 3.87); protons for a terminal methylene group (δ 5.2; 4.9); hydroxyl proton (δ 3.13, disappears on deuteration); protons adjacent to an oxide linkage (δ 3.6) and signals 4-*C*-methyl groups (δ 1.45, δ 1.36, δ 1.07 and δ 0.88).

All the functional groups showed that the furanolactone had a structure very similar to that of methyl angolensate⁶, andirobin⁸ and mahoganin². The hydrogen adjacent to hydroxyl (CHOH) signal at δ 4.48 was very similar to that in swietenine⁹. This suggests

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that it has a $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CHOH}-\text{COOCH}_3$ grouping. The mass spectrum of the compound showed significant peaks at m/e 390 (M-96) and at m/e 348 (M-138). The peak at M-96 could be represented by (II) very similar to that of the mass spectral peak at m/e 374 for methyl angolensate (III).

All these data lead to the formulation of the new furanolactone as 6-hydroxy methyl angolensate. When we were working with the compound, the structure of 6-hydroxy methyl angolensate was reported by Connolly *et al.*⁵ mainly on the basis of N.M.R. data (100 MHz). They isolated it from *Khaya grandifoliola*. The identity of our compound was established by comparing the mixed melting point and T.L.C. data of 6-hydroxy methyl angolensate kindly provided by Dr. K. H. Overton.

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